

Ictal Fear Presenting as Panic Attacks

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Ictal fear is the most frequent type of simple partial seizure and accounts for 60% of all psychiatric aura. Thus, it is not infrequent to be treated as panic attacks (PA). Additionally, the two conditions often co-occur, making differential diagnosis even more difficult.

Objective: A 54-year-old man who presented with depression and PA was studied. The symptomatology will be discussed.

Result: The patient had features that suggest the panic attack was actually ictal fear. The depression responded to mirtazapine 45 mg nocte, however, the panic attacks worsened. The diagnosis of complex partial seizure (CPS) was finally made about 18 months after the initial presentation. His condition greatly improved with sodium valproate 1,500 mg nocte.

Conclusion: Differentiating CPS from panic attacks can be difficult at the initial presentation of the illness. Particular attention should be given to clinical features commonly associated with ictal panic. Otherwise, postictal and interictal panic will become increasingly similar to typical panic attacks.

KEY WORD

ictal fear, complex partial seizure, panic attack, depression, epileptogenesis

INTRODUCTION

It is not infrequent for simple partial seizures of mesial temporal lobe origin presenting as panic episodes to be treated as panic attacks until the patient develops a secondarily generalized tonic-clonic seizure or is witnessed to have a complex partial seizure (CPS). Furthermore, the rates of panic attacks are elevated among individual with epilepsy, and vice versa¹⁾. Therefore, it is important to correctly identify CPS early and to treat it accordingly as CPS itself is associated with elevated rates of anxiety disorders, particularly panic disorder²⁾. Here, we present a case of CPS initially diagnosed as major depressive disorder (MDD) with panic attacks and discuss the symptomatology.

CASE REPORT

A 54-year-old schoolteacher was transferred to a rural school. He commuted 350 km every day by bus. A month later, while traveling on the bus, he suddenly saw a colorful bright light followed by unexplained fear, and palpitations for about 15 seconds, which he attributed to tiredness. The second episode occurred a month later while he was teaching in a classroom. It was preceded by a petrol-like scent which evolved into reduced awareness and unresponsiveness lasting about 20 seconds. He regained full consciousness and noticed slight nausea. Soon he had more such episode until he lost count. Then, he realized his concentration was declining and he had become forgetful of what he was doing as well as what to teach even though he had been teaching the subject for the last 20 years. Consequently, he felt stressed, sad and demotivated. He was referred to psychiatry 6 months after the first episode and was diagnosed with major depressive disorder with panic attacks. Mini-Mental State Examination and Montreal Cognitive Assessment scores were 30/30 indicating no cognitive impairment. He did not comply with

the antidepressant treatment and the condition worsened with panic attacks twice a month. During the subsequent follow-up, his medication was changed to agomelatine and later to mirtazapine up to 45 mg nocte. Beck Depression Inventory score was 12 compared to 24 when he was first seen. A year after the initial presentation, he was not depressed anymore. Nevertheless, panic attacks and memory problem continued and worsening. The panic attacks include symptoms of depersonalization and derealization that occurred up to 3 times per day. The unresponsiveness episodes were by that time noticed by his family members, colleagues, and students. Furthermore, he described episodes in which he had disorientation to place and inability to recognize common tools and their functions during his teaching session. About 18 months after the first presentation, he developed an attack in front of the treating doctor during which he was observed to become unresponsive associated with lip-smacking lasting about 30 seconds. EEG showed sharp slowing at the frontal right side and generalized to left and right, indicating focal seizure with secondary generalization. He was started on sodium valproate 1,500 mg daily. His condition improved with no more panic attacks or memory complaint. Mirtazapine dosage was reduced to 15 mg nocte.

DISCUSSION

One potential barrier to the accurate diagnosis of panic and epilepsy is the limited ability of some patients to report history of symptoms accurately due to the known cognitive deficits common in people with epilepsy³⁾ and the similarity of panic symptoms to certain epilepsy symptoms i.e., ictal fear⁴⁾. Additionally, the two conditions often co-occur^{2,5)}, making differential diagnosis even more difficult.

Psychiatric symptoms or panic attacks, in this case, are classified into ictal, postictal, and interictal in relation to their temporal occurrence to seizures⁵⁾. Ictal panic or fear is a direct manifestation of the sei-

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Table 1. Clinical features of ictal, postictal and interictal panic.⁵⁾

	Ictal panic	Postictal panic	Interictal panic
Prevalence	A most frequent type of simple partial seizures; 60% of all psychiatric auras	10% of individuals with treatment-resistant epilepsy	5.6% of individuals with epilepsy
Duration	Usually less than 30 seconds, 60-90 seconds in CPS, and hours in complex partial status epilepticus	Occurs within 120 hours of a seizure or cluster of seizures	5-20 minutes
Intensity	Mild to moderate; unnatural	Closer to that of ictal panic	Severe; impending doom
Timing	Awake and sleep states	Usually in awake states	Usually in awake states
Stereotypic features	Stereotypic paroxysmal event	May or may not, with respect to duration and associated symptoms.	May or may not, with respect to duration and associated symptoms.
Unresponsiveness	Partially unresponsive and become totally unresponsive as it evolves to a CPS	Usually preserved	Usually preserved
Autonomic symptoms	Paroxysmal salivation is pathognomic in seizures of mesial temporal or insular origin. May be associated with nausea and vomiting.	Not associated with salivation.	Not associated with salivation.
Derealisation, depersonalization, déjà vu, and jamais vu	Ictal activity of mesial temporal origin	May occur	May occur
Agoraphobia	Absent	Common	Common
Automatism	Common	Common	Absent
Age of onset	At any age	At any age	20s-30s
Anticipatory anxiety	Uncommon	Uncommon	Common

zure itself. In contrast, interictal panic occurs independently of seizures and its characteristics are similar to panic disorder. Postictal panic typically occurs within 5 days of seizures and its characteristics are in between ictal fear and interictal panic (table 1).

This case also illustrates the epileptogenesis and the complex interaction with psychosocial stressors, psychiatric symptoms and the treatment⁶⁾. With regard to psychosocial stressors, anxiety was found to be common among the employees⁷⁾ and major life event was associated with depression⁸⁾. There were several lines of evidence to suggest a bidirectional relationship between epilepsy and psychiatric disorders and the possibility of shared factors giving rise to both epilepsy and psychiatric disorders⁹⁾. Aberrant hippocampal neuroplasticity is considered to be a prevalent feature of acquired epilepsy and represents a strong candidate mechanism by which antidepressant drugs might interact with disease processes¹⁰⁾.

CONCLUSION

CPS should be considered as the differential diagnosis of panic attacks, especially if they are associated with clinical features commonly associated with ictal panic. Early recognition and appropriate treatment of CPS would reduce the frequency and severity of neuropsychiatric sequelae.

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